

THE EFFECT OF A HOT/WET ENVIRONMENT ON BONDED COMPOSITE REPAIR JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre/epoxy scarf joints have been exposed to a hot/wet environment for up to twenty three months. Over the first month of exposure joints cured at 170°C showed an increase in strength, which was probably due to the relief of residual curing strains by swelling. A theoretical analysis of this effect compares well with the experimental data. The failure of joints cured at 120°C remained dominated by the adherends, showing a drop in strength of at most 13%. Failure of the joints cured at 170°C becomes dominated by the adhesive, but no significant drop in strength is apparent.

Keywords: repair, environmental effects, swelling, bonded joints, CFRP.

1. INTRODUCTION

As the use of composite materials spreads, the need to understand repair techniques for composites becomes more pressing. All composite components on commercial aircraft have certified repair procedures, but much of the data supporting the certification, and the underlying research, has not appeared in the open literature. This is especially true of the effects of adverse environments on composite repairs. The most common adverse environment is a hot and humid one. Unless an impermeable coating is placed on the exposed surfaces of a composite material, it will absorb moisture from the environment. This absorbed moisture causes swelling and plasticisation of the matrix, which can have detrimental effects on the matrix dominated properties of the composite. Similarly, the absorption of moisture by the adhesive may also cause its plasticisation and swelling.

There are therefore, two competing effects taking place when bonded composite joints are exposed to a hot/wet environment – the effect of moisture on the composite and the effect of moisture on the adhesive. When considering the exposure of repair joints to a hot/wet environment, matters are complicated further by a complex joint geometry.

This paper examines the effect of a hot/wet environment on bonded composite repair joints of carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy (CFRP), with exposure times of up to twenty three months.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 The Repair Joints

The bonded composite repair joints used in this work were typical of depot-level repairs to secondary aircraft structure. All joints were of carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy. One adherend, corresponding to the parent structure to be repaired, was pre-cured, while the other, corresponding to the repair, was co-cured with the adhesive. The joint geometry was based on a scarf joint and is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The geometry of the composite repair joint.

The adherend corresponding to the parent structure was made from unidirectional prepreg, in a quasi-isotropic lay-up. The repair material contained two additional plies. The central portion of the repair had the same lay-up as the parent material. One extra 0° ply was added to each side of the repair, overlapping the ends of the scarf joint by 12.5mm. The repair material was cured under vacuum pressure only, rather than the manufacturer's recommended pressure. Vacuum curing is normal repair practice. This low pressure cure is thought to reduce the strength of the laminate, and so the extra plies were added to ensure that the repair laminate was as strong as the parent structure.

Four joints with different material combinations were studied:

- CFRP co-cured at 120°C, bonded to CFRP pre-cured at 120°C;
- CFRP co-cured at 120°C, bonded to CFRP pre-cured at 170°C;
- CFRP co-cured at 170°C, bonded to CFRP pre-cured at 170°C;
- woven CFRP co-cured at 170°C, bonded to CFRP pre-cured at 170°C.

The adhesives used to bond the repairs had the same cure cycles as the repair materials; thus a repair co-cured at 120°C was bonded with an adhesive cured at 120°C. The adhesives were both modified epoxy film adhesives. The carbon fibre-reinforced prepregs used were "XAS/913" and "XAS/914" and the film adhesives were "BSL312/5" and "BSL 319", all obtained from Ciba-Geigy.

2.2 Testing

Repair joints were tested in tension after various times of exposure to a hot/wet environment. The tensile test method was based on the standard ASTM D 3039, and was carried out on an INSTRON 1186 machine. The dimensions of the test-piece are shown in Figure 2. The environment chosen was 50°C and 84% relative humidity (RH). It has been shown by Collings (1) that a composite exposed to a constant 84% RH will pick up as much moisture at equilibrium as a composite exposed to the worst real world-wide environment. Later Collings showed that the worst European environment is also well modelled by a constant 84% RH (2).

Figure 2. The dimensions of the tensile test-piece.

Specimen width : 25mm

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 The Change in Strength

Table 1. shows the strength of the repair joints exposed to the hot/wet environment. Over the first month an increase in strength is seen for both joints with repairs cured at 170°C. In the 170°C repair using prepreg tape throughout this rise is maintained until about 6 months of exposure, after which strength falls again to stabilise after one year of exposure, with no significant loss of strength. With the 170°C repair using a woven material, the increase in joint strength continues past the first month of exposure. As the exposure time lengthens past one year the average strength appears to fall again, but the experimental scatter is rather large at this point.

Both repairs cured at 120°C show a steady slow decline in strength over the first year of exposure. After this time, the strength appears to stabilise. The 120°C repair to a 120°C cured parent suffered a 10% reduction in strength, while the 120°C repair to a 170°C cured parent suffered a 13% reduction in strength.

Table 1. Tensile strength of repair joints after exposure to a hot/wet environment

Time of Exposure (months)	Failure Load per unit width (kN/m)			
	120°C cured repair on 120°C cured parent	120°C cured repair on 170°C cured parent	170°C cured repair on 170°C cured parent	170°C cured woven repair on 170°C cured parent
0	1480 ± 110	1350 ± 130	1230 ± 60	1070 ± 90
1	1450 ± 170	—	1310 ± 160	—
3	1360 ± 70	1100 ± 150	1280 ± 50	1180 ± 50
6	1450 ± 100	1260 ± 110	1300 ± 40	1100 ± 180
12	1320 ± 120	1180 ± 120	1220 ± 70	1160 ± 40
19	1331 ± 140	—	1220 ± 130	1120 ± 230
23	1360 ± 40	—	1230 ± 70	—

3.2 The Change in Failure Mode

The position of the failures in the unexposed joints seemed to be randomly distributed between the two ends of the scarfed area of the joint, except in the joints using a woven repair, where the failures were more consistently at the end of the top ply of the repair. Delamination, ply splitting and fibre breakage were the main failure mechanisms. There seemed to be little or no failure in the adhesive.

Figure 3. illustrates the typical changes in failure observed after exposure to the hot/wet environment. Detailed observation of the failure surfaces was carried out with a stereo optical microscope. It was therefore possible to determine whether the failure path was through the adhesive (and therefore a cohesive failure), at the interface (interfacial failure), or whether the failure path remained in the composite while running close to the interface. These observations were aided by the fact that one of the adhesives was birefringent, and thus visible when viewed through crossed polarisers.

In repair joints cured at 120°C, the only observable change in the failure was in its position, which became more consistently level with the end of the bottom overlapping repair ply. The major failure modes remained fibre breakage, delamination, and ply splitting. After one year of exposure, more damage occurred in the repair part of the joint, with areas of fibre failure becoming more localised, and less splintered in appearance; delaminations at 0/90 interfaces became more pronounced.

In the repair joints cured at 170°C the amount of cohesive failure in the adhesive increased as the time of exposure increased. This indicated that the adhesive was being plasticised. After 23 months of exposure, damage in repairs using prepreg tape throughout was confined to the repair part of the joint and the adhesive bond. The main path of the failure in joints using a woven repair material remained in the parent material, initiating in the adhesive at the end of the top ply. After 6 months of exposure the failure path remained in the adhesive for up to 10mm before diverting into the parent material.

Figure 3. The Change in Failure Path in Repair Joints Exposed to a Hot/Wet Environment

The thick lines indicate the failure path.
Environment : 50°C, 84% RH.

4. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

The repair joints cured at 170°C both showed an increase in strength over the first month of exposure to a hot/wet environment. This increase in strength may be caused by the relief of curing strains as the composite swells. The effect of this hygrothermal swelling can easily be modelled by classical laminate analysis, and this was done for laminates cured at 170°C.

4.1 Analysis Method

For an isotropic polymer matrix material, it is usually assumed that the swelling strain is related to the volume of water absorbed. This is expressed by Equation 1., overleaf.

$$e_m = \frac{\Delta V}{3 V_0} \quad (1)$$

where: e_m = the matrix swelling strain; ΔV = the volume of water absorbed;
 V_0 = the initial matrix volume.

If it is then assumed that the carbon fibres do not absorb water, equations for the swelling strains of a unidirectional lamina may be derived, as reported by Hahn and Kim (3). Using their results, and relating the swelling to the moisture content in the composite lamina as a whole, the following simple relationship may be derived:

$$e_1 = \beta_1 M \quad \text{and} \quad e_2 = \beta_2 M \quad (2)$$

where: e_1 = the longitudinal swelling in the lamina;
 e_2 = the transverse swelling in the lamina;
 M = the moisture content of the lamina;

$$\beta_1 = \frac{E_m S_c}{3 E_1} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_2 = \frac{1}{3} (1 + \nu_m) S_c \quad (3)$$

where: E_m = Young's modulus of matrix; S_c = specific gravity of the composite;
 E_1 = longitudinal modulus of composite; ν_m = Poisson's ratio of matrix.

The two factors, β_1 and β_2 , are known as the hygrothermal swelling coefficients, and are analogous to the coefficients of thermal expansion. The above relationships (Equation 3.) can be included in a classical laminate analysis, for which the overall equation is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} N \\ M \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon \\ \kappa \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where: [N] = the resultant forces on the laminate; [A] = the extensional stiffness matrix;
[M] = resultant moments on the laminate; [D] = the bending stiffness matrix;
[B] = extension/bending coupling matrix; [ε] = the mid-plane strains;
[κ] = the mid-plane curvatures.

The resultant forces and moments are the sum of all the forces and moments on the laminate, including mechanically applied forces, forces from thermal expansion, and forces from swelling due to absorbed moisture.

Where there is a distribution of moisture through the thickness of the composite, the calculation of resultant forces and moments must take account of the distribution, as reported by Pipes *et al.* (4). Using classical laminate analysis the mid-plane strains and curvatures of the laminate may be found, and from these, the strains and stresses in the individual plies. A failure criterion may then be applied to each ply, and the load may be incremented until a ply failure is detected.

The failure criterion used in this work was the Tsai-Hill failure criterion. This is a simple, easy to use criterion, which nevertheless gives reasonably accuracy in most cases (5). It is assumed that the first failure detected in a ply is a matrix or an interface failure, so that the ply can no-longer carry shear or transverse loads. The stiffness matrix for the failed ply is then modified and the calculation continued. Failure of the laminate is assumed to occur either when all the plies have failed once, or when a second failure is detected in a ply. This scheme has been successfully used in previous analyses (6, 7).

The properties used in this analysis are shown in Table 2. It is assumed that the laminates absorb moisture according to Fickian diffusion. The diffusion coefficient and the maximum moisture content are also shown in Table 2. Although in the calculation of the mid-plane strains and curvatures the real moisture distribution was used, in the calculation of individual ply strains an average moisture level

was used for each ply. It is thought that this approximation will not significantly affect the results. Two laminates were analysed, corresponding to the parent laminate and the repair laminate. Only composites cured at 170°C were modelled, as moisture absorption in this material is a close approximation to Fickian diffusion. Moisture absorption in the composite cured at 120°C was not Fickian in character, and the diffusion coefficient appeared to be dependent on the local moisture concentration (8). As the internal moisture distribution could not be predicted with any confidence, the effects of swelling were not assessed for laminated cured at 120°C.

Table 2. Properties of 170°C curing CFRP used in analysis

Property	Parent	Repair	units
0° modulus, E_1	132.8	126.2	GPa
90° modulus, E_2	7.0	6.7	GPa
shear modulus, G_{12}	3.7	3.5	GPa
0° tensile strength, X	1879	1785	MPa
0° compressive strength, X'	1350	1283	MPa
90° tensile strength, Y	79	75	MPa
90° compressive strength, Y'	230	219	MPa
shear strength, S	50	48	MPa
0° thermal expansion coefficient, α_1	- 0.45	- 0.45	$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$
90° thermal expansion coefficient, α_2	28.0	28.0	$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$
0° hygrothermal expansion coefficient, β_1	0.012	0.012	-
90° hygrothermal expansion coefficient, β_2	0.682	0.682	-
Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	0.32	0.32	-
modulus of matrix, E_m	3.00	3.00	GPa
specific gravity of composite, S_c	1.55	1.55	-
diffusion coefficient, D	2.08×10^{-7}	3.95×10^{-7}	mm^2/s
maximum moisture content, M	1.37	1.29	%

4.2 Comparison with Experimental Results

Table 3. shows the analytical results and the corresponding experimental results. These are also shown in graphical form in Figure 4. A similar rise in strength is found in the analytical results to that which was seen experimentally in joints cured at 170°C. The agreement between the theoretical strength of the quasi-isotropic parent laminate and the experimentally measured strength of both the parent laminate and the repair joint is very good. The analytical and experimental results for the repair

Table 3. Theoretical and experimental failure loads of 170°C cured parent and repair laminates

Exposure Time (days)	Theoretical Failure Load (MN/m)		Experimentally Measured Failure Load (MN/m)		
	Quasi-isotropic $(\pm 45/0/90)_{2s}$	Repair Material $(0(\pm 45/0/90)_{2s})_s$	Quasi-isotropic $(\pm 45/0/90)_{2s}$	Repair Material $(0(\pm 45/0/90)_{2s})_s$	Repair Joint
0	1.180	1.545	1.25 ± 0.10	1.85 ± 0.05	1.23 ± 0.04
5	1.246	1.624	-	-	-
10	1.246	1.624	-	-	-
30	1.252	1.627	-	-	1.31 ± 0.15
60	1.244	1.618	-	-	-
90	1.241	1.616	-	-	1.28 ± 0.02
180	1.239	1.616	1.33 ± 0.04	1.83 ± 0.14	1.30 ± 0.02

Figure 4. Theoretical and experimental failure loads for 170°C cured laminates and repair joints

laminates show the same trends, although the repair is in fact stronger than predicted. The basic strengths and stiffnesses used to calculate the strength of the repair laminate were assumed to be 95% of the values for the parent laminate. This reduction was to take account of any loss in strength due to the vacuum cure of the repair. From the data presented the 5% reduction in properties appears to be too much.

5. DISCUSSION

Before exposure of the repair joints to a hot/wet environment, the bonding adhesive plays very little part in the joint failure. The failure is governed by the strength of the patch and parent laminates, and the dry joint strength closely reflects the strength of the dry quasi-isotropic parent laminate. In order to find out if the swelling of the laminate is affecting the observed strength of the joint, the first analysis must be of the parent and patch adherends. If hygrothermal swelling is affecting the parent and repair laminates it may also be influencing the strength of the exposed repair joints. The increase in strength, both predicted and measured is not very great, being between 4% and 6%. This order of strength increase agrees closely with the results reported by Browning and co-workers (9). Analyses to predict more accurately the strength of the repair joint after exposure to a hot/wet environment should include the adhesive and the joint geometry explicitly, as the stress concentrations in the joint may be significantly changed by the swelling.

Hygrothermal swelling is probably playing a part in the effects seen at short exposure times (less than three months), by relieving residual curing stresses, as evidenced by the close correlation of the theoretical and experimental data for laminates cured at 170°C. After six months of exposure the moisture content of the repair joints is at a maximum, and thus any further change in joint properties must be due to a degradation of the properties of the composite and/or adhesive rather than the effect of a change in the residual stresses. The degree of plasticisation in the adhesive may continue to increase beyond this time limit, as it absorbs moisture more slowly, and has less surface exposed to the humid environment. With increasing exposure time the moisture may also start to attack the adhesive/composite interface.

No failure in the adhesive is seen before exposure to a hot/wet environment, but after exposure, a significant amount of cohesive failure in the adhesive occurs. This is clear experimental evidence that the 170°C curing adhesive is plasticised by exposure to a hot/wet environment. The amount of cohesive failure in this adhesive increases with exposure time, but because this is not the only change in the system, there is no straightforward relationship between the area of cohesive failure and the exposure time. Nor does the increasing amount of adhesive failure reduce the failure load in all cases. Adhesive plasticisation appears to decrease the effect of the stress concentration at the end of the overlapping repair plies, leading to the increase in strength seen in 170°C repair using woven material.

The behaviour observed in repairs cured at 120°C seems to be dominated by the composite adherends. There is no evidence of adhesive plasticisation after exposure, and the failure mode remains unchanged. The effect of hygrothermal swelling on laminates cured at 120°C was not analysed, as the internal moisture distribution could not be predicted with any confidence. Swelling of the composite will still occur as moisture is absorbed, with the resultant relief of residual curing

strains. However, if the properties of the composite matrix are seriously affected by the absorbed moisture, the expected increase in strength will not be apparent. While this is a plausible explanation for the experimental results for joints cured at 120°C, this study can provide no evidence to support the hypothesis.

6. CONCLUSIONS

- The repair joints studied all show very good durability in a hot/wet environment. Joints cured at 120°C showed at most a 13% decrease in strength, while of the joints cured at 170°C, one showed no significant strength degradation, and the other increased in strength.
- The strength of all the repair joints studied appears to stabilise after 12 months of exposure.
- The adhesive cured at 170°C is plasticised by exposure to a hot/wet environment, while the adhesive cured at 120°C is not.
- The repair joints cured at 170°C increase in strength for the first month of exposure, because the swelling of the composite caused by the absorption of water relieves the residual curing strains.
- Repair joints cured at 120°C decrease in strength for the first year of exposure, but the failure mode does not change.

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